

UNDERSTANDING COMMUNAL CLASHES DURING RELIGIOUS PROCESSIONS

REPORT ON THE BRAJMANDAL JALABHISHEK YATRA, 2024

Rashad Ullah Khan

In Collaboration with : IMRC (Indian Muslim Relief & Charities)

WORKING PAPER

ISSUE - 04 | OCTOBER - 2024 | VOLUME - 04

In collaboration
with

CDPP

CENTRE FOR
DEVELOPMENT
POLICY AND
PRACTICE

UNDERSTANDING COMMUNAL CLASHES DURING RELIGIOUS PROCESSIONS

REPORT ON THE BRAJMANDAL JALABHISHEK YATRA, 2024

Rashad Ullah Khan

In Collaboration with : IMRC (Indian Muslim Relief & Charities)

WORKING PAPER SERIES

ISSUE - 04 | OCTOBER - 2024 | VOLUME - 04

Abstract

India's secular and pluralistic identity is under severe strain due to escalating communal tensions, particularly from groups aiming to instigate violence. The rise of communal sentiments during the Bharatiya Janata Party's rule has increased anxiety among minority communities. One tactic employed to fuel discord is the organization of armed religious processions. Groups such as Bajrang Dal and Vishwa Hindu Parishad have been leading these processions more frequently, often resulting in violence and chaos.

One notable incident was the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra in Nuh, Haryana, on July 31, 2023, which sparked clashes between procession participants and local Muslim residents. In 2024, the procession was scheduled again, but this time it proceeded peacefully, concluding without any communal violence. This paper aims to explore why the 2024 event was different, examining factors such as the contrasting approaches of the administration and police, the specific elements present in the 2023 procession that were absent in 2024, and the local context that contributed to heightened communal tensions. By addressing these questions, the paper seeks to shed light on how a religious procession, typically a spiritual act, can devolve into a trigger for communal conflict.

Keywords: communal, processions, violence, conflict, minority, Meo-Muslims, provocative, slogans, law and order

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	I
1. Introduction	01
2. Historicising Politicised Religious Processions in India: Their Origin and Purpose	02
3. Modern-Day Avatar of Religious Processions: Planned and Organised Violence	03
4. Implementation of Law for Regulation of Religious Processions	04
5. The Aftermath of Religious Processions: Examining Fact Finding reports	05
6. Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra 2023: Context and Causes of Violence	06
7. Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra 2024: Peaceful Procession under State Supervision	07
7.1 Flower Showering and Refreshment Stalls	10
7.2 Visit to Nalhar Mahadev Temple	10
7.3 Conversation with the Muslim Residents of Nuh on Last Year's Violence	11
7.4 Passing through Nagina	14
7.5 Spiritual Nature of Yatris in Jhir Temple of Firozpur Jhirka	14
7.6 Conversation with Police and Residents of Firozpur Jhirka	15
7.7 Post Procession Discussions with Residents of Nuh	15
7.8 Nationalism as a Defense	16
7.9 Brotherhood across Faiths within the Context of Nuh	16
7.10 How Is the State Perceived? Who Is the State Safeguarding?	17
7.11 Religious Rituals in Public Spaces	18
8. Takeaways	
8.1 Role of Administration and Police in Maintaining Law and Order	18
8.2 Depoliticised Procession due to the Absence of Militant Hindutva Organisations in the Organising Committee	19
8.3 Role of the Muslims in Ensuring Peace and Brotherhood Prevailed	19
9. Conclusion	19
References	

1. Introduction

The pluralistic and secular characteristic of India has been facing its most intense challenge as of late—with communal forces attempting to create an environment where violence could erupt at any given time. The process of communalisation that has been taking place during the reign of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) (“Religious Freedom Worsened,” 2022) has increased fear and insecurity among the minority communities. One of the tools being utilised to further worsen harmony and peace is the use of religious processions. Armed religious processions being carried out by militant Hindutva groups such as the Bajrang Dal and Vishwa Hindu Parishad (VHP) have become more and more frequent in the past few years, leaving behind a trail of violence and destruction.

One such procession which created quite a stir was the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra that was carried out in Nuh, Haryana on July 31, 2023. As the procession was being carried out in Nuh, communal clashes broke out between the members of the procession and the Muslim residents of that area. The harrowing aspect of the communal clash was that the violence boiled over and made its way to Gurugram (Jain, 2023), a prosperous business hub, right next to India's capital Delhi. All of this took place one month before India hosted the G20 summit in Delhi (Farooqui, 2023). Such is the sociopolitical climate of India and callous attitude of the administration, which enables such communal clashes to take place.

In 2024, it was announced that Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra would be organised again. However, the 2024 iteration of the religious procession went through Nuh peacefully and the procession concluded without a single incident of communal violence. This report, written by the Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP), aims to inquire into why no violence took place when the same procession was organised in 2024. The report aims to answer questions such as, what were the differences in the attitudes and manner in which the administration and the police operated, what elements within the religious procession were present in 2023 and not in 2024, and what was the ground level context due to which communal tensions were high. The answers to these questions and other related questions will enable us to understand how a religious procession, a ritual act which is supposed to be spiritual in nature, instead becomes a preliminary act of instigation which leads to communal clashes.

The report goes into detail about the history of politicised religious processions in the context of India, its genesis, and what it intended to counter. It will also cover the use of religious processions by various right-wing Hindutva groups and how it has been an

effective tool to mobilise people under the garb of religion, while the intention has been far more sinister. A team from CDPP was present in Nuh during the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra that took place on July 22, 2024, and they observed the procession while engaging with the Muslim residents of Nuh, Firozpur Jhirka, and a few neighbouring towns. The conversations with the

residents give an insight into how religious processions are politicised with the involvement of militant Hindutva groups, which then leads to communal violence. An exploration into the themes related to religious processions and their aftermath is extremely crucial during this juncture, especially in the context of how the Indian society is becoming more and more polarised.

2. Historicising Politicised Religious Processions in India: Their Origin and Purpose

It is interesting to note that the use of religious processions to incite conflict has been present in the Indian context since as early as 1893. The Ganapati festival processions are the first instance of how religious processions were weaponised in order to give rise to a form of “Hindu consciousness” and create social divide. The Shia festival of Muharram, historically, was an inter-community festival in Poona. The festival would be filled with Hindu musicians performing, Hindu women hired as dancers, and Hindu laborers employed to carry the symbolic biers on their bullock carts (Tejani, 2007).

Dr. Shabnum Tejani analysed colonial documents and showed that the number of Hindu processions in celebration of Muharram would outnumber the ones carried out by the Muslims, a classic example of the nature of syncretic traditions in India. However, this all came to an end with the transformation and politicisation of the Ganapati festival. It had historically been celebrated in a quasi-public manner (Kaur, 2005) and was later re-introduced as a public festival under the leadership of Bal Gangadhar Tilak. The festival which earlier involved only the local kinship groups who were in close proximity to each other became a festival in which all Hindu classes could participate together. The new version of the now public festival was modeled after Muharram and with it followed campaigns intended to dissuade Hindus from participating in an “Islamic” festival and disgracing the Hindu religion that they belonged to (Tejani, 2007).

Tejani writes about how the Ganapati festival's transformation was an attempt to reinvent and politicise an established ritual which would prevent Hindus from participating in festivals of the other community. The festival, apart from creating a separation based on religion, also severed long-standing economic ties shared within the space's members. Different Hindu traders who would interact with the Muslims, now have their attention devoted to the Ganapati festivals, creating insular communities. The main impact of the Ganapati festival, Tejani writes, was the creation of an ideological space that would allow for the rhetoric of inter-community hate and language that would identify the Muslims as outsiders and not intrinsic to India. While the Ganapati festivals saw reduced participation over the years, the idea behind the festival has been revived and used to incite communal tensions among the masses.

We see that communalism manifests itself in the society through the use of religious festivals especially processions in order to intimidate the minority Muslim community. Dr. Ghanshyam Shah (1970) through his work shows how there is a lot of evidence to suggest that communal organisations such as the Rashtriya Samiti Sangh coordinated with the local administration and

the police to organise and incite communal violence. Shah emphasises that the most disturbing manifestation was the use of religious processions in front of mosques and playing music which would hurt the sensibilities of the Muslim community. The use of religious processions and music by communal organisations in order to intimidate or incite communal violence was also seen during the politicisation of the Ganpati festivals in the context of Maharashtra during the 1890s as written by Tejani (2007). Slowly, we see how processions are used more and more by political actors with the support of communal militant organisations as time passes by. By contextualising the history of how politicised religious processions rose in prominence and were used by militant Hindutva groups, we can see how the word “yatra” now either has the connotation of a pilgrimage or procession carried out by a religious institution or an ethnoreligious demonstration by Hindu militant organisations (Jaffrelot, 2009). Dr. Christophe Jaffrelot theorised about how the Hindu pilgrimage is used politically due to its territorial characteristics that allow for it to be viewed in ethnonationalist terms in the case of pan-Indian yatras. It is for this reason that majoritarian elements try to use processions for their own political ends and to spread communalism.

The work done by Jaffrelot (1998) tells us about how Hindu processions are miniature level pilgrimages that are organised to worship a deity. The two important features that these processions display is the fact they seem to be socially inclusive, with members of all castes taking part in them, and that they aid in the process of demarcating space which can be labeled as exclusively belonging to the Hindu community. It is these features that make processions so attractive to militant Hindu groups as they view them with the potential of turning them into Hindu activist events, in the same manner that was done by Bal Gangadhar Tilak.

Jaffrelot (2009) historicises various yatras that were employed by Hindu activists to first unite the Hindu nationalist movements and then employ the processions to foster communalism. He writes about the Ekatmata Yatra (March for Unity) that was carried out by the Vishwa Hindu Parishad (VHP), an offshoot of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh, to ensure that the Hindu populations across areas would engage with each other and this would help in fostering unity. The success of the yatra could be seen as it turned into a nationwide mass demonstration and laid the foundation for this brand of ethnoreligious movements to gain more political mileage. This success was followed by the Rath Yatra in 1990, which was a perfect mixture of religion and politics led by BJP leader L. K. Advani. The two aims of the Rath Yatra were to counter the increased divisions that were becoming apparent among the Hindus due to the recommendations given by the Mandal Commission, and to mobilize Hindus around the issue of the Ram Mandir in Ayodhya. The overall aim was to effectively unite the Hindu community against their common enemy, the Muslims.

It is very clear to see that a political purpose has been denoted to the use of processions, whether it was done in the context of the Ganpati festivals during the colonial period, or during the mid-1960s where Hindu processions were carried out in front of mosques or more recently when they were used by Hindu activists in order to demarcate space as exclusively theirs. In all different contexts, we see common features of provocation, violence, and anti-minority sentiment present.

3. Modern-Day Avatar of Religious Processions: Planned and Organised Violence

India has always been a plural country of rich diverse cultures and practices. However, with diversity comes conflict and Indian history shows how religion has very often been used to incite violence and hate. When the Hindu festivals of Ram Navami and Hanuman Jayanti were celebrated in 2022, the country again witnessed communal violence on a large scale. A detailed report prepared by Citizens & Lawyers Initiative (2023) on the clashes titled the “Routes of Wrath: Weaponizing Religious Processions” (“Report by Citizen-Lawyer Collective,” 2023) shows how communal violence occurred in nine states across India while there were instances of provocation and low-level violence in another three states. The violence was triggered in the conflict-affected areas due to the passage of religious processions, as part of the festivities of Ram Navami and Hanuman Jayanti, specifically through Muslim dominated neighborhoods. The report investigated the assaults and shows us that the prime factor for communal violence and riots that occurred in the context of religious processions was the routes that were chosen by the organisers of the processions. The work done by Iyer and Shrivastava (2017) shows us that religious riots and conflicts have become a tool for political parties to create social divide thus influencing voter behaviour by raising communal issues.

These organisers receive backing from militant Hindutva organisations and claim that their processions are integral to the practice of their faith and a celebration of God (Chakraborty, 2023). The procession is portrayed as an innocent ritual celebration of God with the onus of the violence that follows placed on those who challenge the procession. Unfortunately, this is far from the truth. The Routes of Wrath report draws parallels between the manner in which these religious processions are carried out in different states in India. The religious processions would always comprise of large mobs of men dressed in saffron coloured clothing, carrying swords, trishuls, and in some cases firearms. The route that would be taken by these gatherings would always pass through Muslim-dominated neighbourhoods and the major mosques which were in the vicinity. Rather than singing and celebrating God, the members of the procession would be devoted to raising provocative slogans targeting the Muslim community, slogans related to a demand for Hindu Rashtra, and the conditions that the Muslims would have to live in after it is achieved. The processions would also be accompanied with speakers and megaphones which would play anti-Muslim hate music (Pandit, 2022) at high volumes.

In 2022, both the festivals of Ram Navami and Hanuman Jayanti took place during the month of Ramzan, a holy month for the Muslim community. The processions would target mosques during the times of prayer or during the time the fast was meant to be broken, playing loud hate-filled music in front of mosques and raising slogans. The timing would allow the procession mob to incite confrontation and conflict with a large gathering of people from the Muslim community. We see that the religious processions become what Gaborieau (1985) terms as “Rituals of Provocation” which led to communal violence. Peter van der Veer (1996) states that the riots that occur due to these rituals of provocation are integral in the construction of public space, which

further define the conceptions of community within that area. The works of Gaborieau and van der Veer are extremely relevant to the ground reality which the Routes of Wrath report studies. The report indicates that the combination of the saffron mob with weapons, raising of provocative slogans, and loud hate-filled music in Muslim-dominated areas incites violence. The garb of religious festivities is used as a cover to start communal violence which further leads to loss of property, as the shops, homes, and religious places of Muslims are targeted. We see how the public space is constructed in a manner that forces members of the Muslim community to live intimidated by the majority Hindu community.

4. Implementation of Law for Regulation of Religious Processions

In the background of all the violence and turmoil that took place in 2022 during the Ram Navami and Hanuman Jayanti processions, the Citizens for Justice and Peace (CJP) had filed a Public Interest Litigation (PIL) before the Supreme Court (Maniyar, 2023). The intention with which the CJP approached the Supreme Court was to ensure that the court would issue detailed guidelines and formulate a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) on the route to be allowed/ followed by the procession and that the members of the procession be unarmed as per law.

The petition very importantly highlighted “Justice D. P. Madon Commission of Inquiry,” which had recommended that processions which are likely to provoke communal trouble, need a proper risk assessment from the side of the police before the permission can be granted. The D. P. Madon Commission of Inquiry stated that the police should undertake an assessment of the routes before permission is given to the organisers of the procession. The petition also relied on an advisory released by the Ministry of Home Affairs in 2019, and guidelines issued by the Punjab Police in 2018. The advisory of the Ministry of Home Affairs clearly states that those who indulge in the illegal firing of weapons during marriages, public gatherings, religious places/processions, parties, political rallies etc. violate the provisions of the Arms Act, 1959, and the licenses of the perpetrators must be cancelled in accordance with the law. The guidelines by the Punjab Police focus on the regulation of processions/assemblies/protests/demonstrations/dharnas/marches, etc., giving instructions on what police officers need to do to deal with processions and preventing them from turning unruly and violent. Starting with the legal prohibition against carrying of arms and lathis, the Guidelines also emphasise that entire processions need to be videographed, and organisers need to give undertakings to ensure lawful behavior and conduct. The Punjab Police guidelines also put the onus on the organisers to ensure that “no inflammatory speech or any unlawful activity is done at the venue of procession or assembly, which may cause tension in the area or create mutual hatred or create differences amongst different communities, castes, groups, religions etc.”

The petition by the CJP was dismissed by the Supreme Court, on the grounds that the state officials would understand more about the local context and factors and would be more

competent in handling these issues (Rajagopal, 2023). However, the petition raises a lot of important questions that need further consideration. The most important fact that the petition highlights by asking the Supreme Court to issue a Standard Operating Procedure on how processions are organised, is that there is no uniform or set form of guidelines from the side of the government for the organisation of religious processions. Justice Lalitha Kanneganti of the Telangana High Court had observed that there was no rationale behind the process of granting permissions to religious processions and programmes by the police in Hyderabad (Ramu, 2022) and this reflects how country-wide, there is a dire need for the formulation of guidelines. The petition states that the court needs to examine the religious processions and violence left in their wake and consider the following questions (CJP, 2022):

1. Who granted permission for their possessions?
2. Was permission granted at all?
3. Who allowed/granted permission for arms to be carried in this procession?
4. Was or has penal action been initiated following the outbreaks?
5. Who has permitted “trishul diksha” when intimidatory remarks threatening to exterminate an entire community of Indians have been made?
6. Has there been any lawful prosecution and prevention of such blatant arms distribution assemblies?
7. Has there been any action against police officers or members of the administration for failure to perform their lawful and statutory duties?

5. The Aftermath of Religious Processions: Examining Fact Finding Reports

It is important to look at the aftermath of some of the recent religious processions that have taken place to understand how the minority community is not only affected during the procession, but also after. The main contention with how religious processions have become weaponised is not the violence and conflict that occurs but the capturing of spaces, villainisation, and marginalisation of the Muslim minority community that follows.

The fact-finding report constituted by the Centre for Study of Society and Secularism (2022) shows how in the case of Khargone (“Khargone Violence Fact Finding,” 2023) Madhya Pradesh, the communal violence was engineered by the Hindutva militant organisations and the state which had the BJP in power. After the processions, the blame for the communal clashes that took place was bestowed upon the Muslim community by the police and the state administration. After the communal violence in Khargone due to the Ram Navami procession, the report shows that intense economic marginalisation of the Muslim community took place, and the community also suffered great losses in terms of property of both homes and commercial establishments. The state-led demolition drives that targeted the commercial establishments and homes of the Muslim

community was an attack against the basic requirements of security, livelihood, and shelter making them economically vulnerable. The act of demolition drives became a form of state policy which acted as a form of collective punishment against the minority community.

Another example is of the fact-finding report of the Centre for Study of Society and Secularism (2023) related to the procession violence in Vadodara (“Vadodara Ram Navami,” 2023) Gujarat, which shows how during the communal clashes the procession would on purpose pass through areas of the Muslim community. Members of the VHP who were questioned by the fact-finding team demanded why they should not be allowed to pass through Muslim areas. This tone suggests that there is a sense of entitlement the VHP has to the spaces occupied by the Muslim community even though they knew they did not have the permission to do so. The role of the police is also questionable—as they clearly sided with the state administration and those taking part in the procession. The police were not proactive in stopping the procession from diverting its route and played virtually no role in stopping the violence. Post the violence, the number of First Information Reports filed by the police against the Muslim community far outnumbered those filed against members of the procession who diverted from the route and played a huge role in the violence that unfolded.

6. Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra 2023: Context and Causes of Violence

Before we delve into what took place in 2023, it is important to have a historical context of the social makeup of Nuh. The Meo-Muslims constitute the majority in the Nuh region, and the work done by Dr. Mukesh Kumar (2019) goes into extensive detail about how in between the thirteenth and nineteenth centuries, the Meo community underwent socioeconomic and religious changes leading to members of the community converting to Islam. However, Dr. Kumar notes that while they would religiously identify as Muslims, the Meos were still both Hindu and Muslim in terms of their cultural and religious practises. This is a good example of how syncretic traditions exist in the Indian context, giving India its plural characteristic.

During the time of partition, Gandhiji had famously termed the Mewat region, under which Nuh falls, as Bharat ki Reed ki Haddi (India's Backbone). The Meo-Muslims were under scrutiny by the administration and were accused of wanting to join Pakistan. Even with allegations levelled against them and the violence they encountered during that era, the Meo-Muslims chose to stay in India (Centre for Study of Secularism and Society, 2023).

It is important to note that the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra was first organised by the VHP in 2021 (Akhtar, 2023) with the agenda of reviving ancient Hindu temples and increasing religious tourism in the Mewat area (“Started as Pilgrimage,” 2023). The yatra begins from the Nalhar Mahadev Temple in Nuh, passing through the Jhir Temple and ending at the Radhe Krishna

Mandir in Singhana. The immediate origin of the violence on July 31, 2023, is still contested by both sides. However, both sides agree that there had been an increase in animosity and buildup of tension among the communities before the yatra took place (Association for Protection of Civil Rights, 2023). The fact-finding report of the Centre for Study of Secularism and Society (2023) goes into detail about how communalism was stoked before the yatra:

A couple of days before the procession on 31st July 2023, in a video, Monu Manesar, a fugitive who was wanted in the murder of Junaid and Nasir, had urged his followers to be present in the Braj Mandal Jal Abhishek procession as he will be attending it. This inflamed tempers of a section of Muslims in the region. Similarly, on the morning of 31st July, in a video Bittu Bajrangi challenged the Muslim community to welcome him with flowers and gave out his location. He said, “Apke jijaji aa rahe hai. Phoolonse Swagat ke liye khade rahe na.”

The video challenge from Monu Manesar, who is said to be involved in the murder of two Muslim youth, played a large role in provoking the violence. The violence spilled over to Sohna and Gurugram (“Clashes Break Out,” 2023), that resulted in the loss of about six lives. Post-violence, the police arrested approximately 156 Muslims in Nuh who, according to the fact-finding report of Association for Protection Civil Rights (2023), were randomly arrested in a very one-sided crackdown. The Muslims also faced the wrath of the administration in terms of having their properties, which included shops, houses, and stalls of small businesses, demolished.

Source: *Times of India*

What is important to note is the absence of Nuh's Superintendent of Police when the violence broke out (Nuh Police Chief, 2023). The lack of police presence was one of the major reasons why such a large-scale incident took place. Due to the lack of police supervision, many incidents of provocation from the side of the religious procession went unchecked and eventually led to violence. As the fact-finding report from the Centre for Study of Secularism and Society (2023) states:

So far, barring vandalizing of a mazaar near the Nalhar Shiva temple last year, there was no history of violence during the yatra. The procession or yatra started from civil lines in Gurugram on the morning of 31st July. The yatra was to reach Ferozepur Jhirka via Nuh. After performing the Jal Abhishek at the Nalhar Shiv temple, the participants of the procession returned to Nuh city at around 2.30 pm. Some participants were carrying arms—swords, lathis and guns when the procession entered Nuh. They raised anti-Muslim slogan—“Mulle Kate Jayenge, Ram Ram chillayenge” rented the air.

As discussed earlier, the carrying of weapons and provocative slogans are features present in religious processions organised by militant Hindutva organisations such as the VHP and Bajrang Dal. The rise in communal tensions due to the video provocation by Monu Manesar, lack of police presence to maintain law and order, presence of weapons, and use of provocative slogans led to chaos which subsequently reached all the way to Gurugram. It is important to first understand what went wrong in 2023, in order to understand how the 2024 iteration of the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra was so different, with the differences being very apparent.

7. Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra 2024: Peaceful Procession under State Supervision

When it was announced that the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra would again take place in 2024, many were concerned due to what had transpired the year before. However, the seriousness with which the administration was monitoring the procession was apparent from the beginning. Before the yatra was to take place on July 22, both the Gurugram and Nuh police had announced that they would be using drones to monitor the yatra and to ensure that no communal escalation took place (“Officials to Use Drones,” 2024). Considering what had happened the previous year and how social media was used to spread misinformation about what had taken place, the Haryana government had ordered the suspension of mobile internet and bulk SMS services in the Nuh District (“Braj Mandal Yatra,” 2024). Additionally, over 2,000 personnel from the police and paramilitary were deployed in the region. From Sohna onwards, there were security checks after every 3 kms and armed security personnel were present in key junctions. Another key difference between 2023 and 2024 was the group in charge of organising the yatra. In 2024, the yatra was being organised by a composite group consisting of members from the Khap Panchayat and religious leaders, instead of the VHP and the Bajrang Dal (Kissu, 2024). The administration had also notified the organisers that permission had only been granted for the yatra and that DJs, loudspeakers, and weapons such as talwars and lathis were prohibited.

Source: *The New Indian Express*

The yatris would travel to all three temples using buses, cars, and bikes as the total distance of the yatra, visiting all three temples starting from Nuh, would be around 80 kms.

7.1 Flower Showering and Refreshment Stalls

As we (the CDPP team) made our way towards Nuh, there were stalls every 2–3 kms where the Muslim residents of Nuh were showering the yatris with flowers and providing them with refreshments (“Braj Mandal Yatra,” 2024). This was being done in order to display that there was no ill will towards those who were participating in the procession. Members of the yatra were also appreciative of the same and were pleasantly conversing with those who were hosting them. During our stop at one of the flower showering and refreshment stops, a television media interview with one of the stall organisers was taking place. In his interview, he stated emphatically how what transpired last year left a bad mark in the history of Nuh, which otherwise is a very peaceful area and in order to dispel the allegations that the residents of Nuh were violent, this year they have taken this proactive measure to ensure that no violence takes place and that the yatris are made to feel welcome. We saw many of the stalls on the way to Nuh, at Nagina, and in the vicinity of Firozpur Jhirka.

7.2 Visit to Nalhar Mahadev Temple

We went and visited the Nalhar Mahadev Temple in Nuh, which was the first stop of the procession. The temple was on the outskirts of Nuh and immediately one could sense that the police were being extremely vigilant. They were guiding the buses which were carrying the yatris and ensuring that the road to the temple did not become congested. There was an abundance of police in front of the temple and in the surrounding areas, equipped with lathis and guns,

Flower Showering and Refreshment Stall. Source: CDPP Team.

symbolising how the police wanted to ensure that no incident took place. As we made our way inside the temple, the yatriks were taking part in the jalabhishek (offering water to the shivling) and the whole exercise was very spiritual in nature. Devotional songs were being performed on a stage which had been set up inside the mandir area. The organisers were making constant announcements asking those who had already performed the jalabhishek to make their way to the next temple in Firozpur Jhirka, in order to avoid overcrowding. An interesting incident that took place was that the organisers also announced that they had received information from the police that some members of the yatra were shouting provocative slogans or devotional slogans aggressively at the residents of Nuh. The organisers stated that those who were doing this would be promptly picked up by the police and that there would be no leniency related to this act of disruption. This goes to show that there was strong will from the side of the organisers as well to ensure that the yatra would be spiritual in nature.

7.3 Conversation with the Muslim Residents of Nuh on Last Year's Violence

After leaving the Nalhar Mahadev temple at Nuh, we made our way to the chowk where the main incident of rioting and violence had taken place in Nuh. At the chowk, one could see a sea of police uniforms along with the presence of Rapid Action Force team. We conversed with a shopkeeper whose shop was facing the chowk, and he told us how this was the area the violence and rioting was limited to and the rest of Nuh was unaffected. When we asked him for how long this yatra had been taking place, he replied that this was a relatively new yatra he had seen only the

Yatris offering “jalabhishek” inside the Nalhar Mahadev Temple, Nuh. Source: CDPP Team.

last 2–3 years. We asked him what he thought was the reason for last year's violence, and he said it mainly took place due to how Monu Manesar challenged the residents of Nuh to welcome him when he came to Nuh. That had raised the communal tensions along with the nature of the procession which consisted of loudspeakers playing anti-Muslim music. The shopkeeper also stated how many of the yatris had weapons and lathis and were constantly shouting “Jai Shri Ram” loudly at the residents.

When asked about whether he had a problem with the procession in general, the shopkeeper replied that there was no such feeling among the people of Nuh. They had always been receptive to the Kanwar Yatra that takes place every year, putting up tents so that the yatris could rest and receive refreshments. The difference between the Kanwar Yatra and the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra was its character, with the Kanwar Yatra being more spiritual in nature and the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra having clear political motives. The shopkeeper also added that Nuh had always been a place where Muslims and Hindus had resided peacefully, and it was the outsiders who had come to take part in the procession who had ruined the image of Nuh. When asked how the relationship between the Hindus and Muslims and Nuh was post-violence, he said that the relationship between the locals had not changed at all, Muslims from Nuh had been visiting and still visited the Nalhar Mahadev Temple and the Hindu residents of Nuh would also take part during the time of Eid.

We had noticed that all the shops in Nuh had been closed, with the streets of Nuh being completely empty. A few of the elderly residents of Nuh were positioned every 100–200 metres along the main road of Nuh. When we asked if the administration had asked for a bandh in Nuh, the shop owner replied that this was a conscious decision taken by the residents of Nuh, to further limit the possibility of any provocation or negative engagement taking place between the residents of Nuh and the members of the procession. The shop owner said that after what took place last year, the residents of Nuh were determined to dispel all the negative comments that had been made against the Meo-Muslims of Nuh, claiming they were violent and disruptive.

During our conversation with another shop owner, he stated how with VHP and Bajrang Dal not taking part in organising the yatra, it was very clear that there were no intentions of disrupting the peace that was present in Nuh. While this conversation was taking place, a group of 40–50 Bajrang Dal members assembled at the chowk and began sloganeering “Jai Shri Ram” and “Har Har Mahadev.” The police were on their toes, and it was clear that sloganeering was all that they would be doing. After 10 minutes, the police cleared the Bajrang Dal members. We overheard a television interview one of the members from the Bajrang Dal was giving to the media, where he placed the blame on last year's incident only on the Muslim residents of Nuh. He stated that the Muslims of Nuh should be supportive of the yatra as it would increase tourism and then further lead to development of the area. Here again, the vigilance of the police was clear to see as they did not let the sloganeering escalate to a larger issue. After the sloganeering, the shopkeeper exclaimed that this year the Bajrang Dal members would not be able to do anything that could lead to violence as the police would set them straight.

Bajrang Dal members sloganeering at the chowk. Source: CDPP Team.

7.4 Passing through Nagina

As we made our way to the Jhir Temple in Firozpur Jhirka, we stopped at the town of Nagina which was on the way. There we conversed with a local school teacher and asked him his views about the procession. He said the procession never reached Nagina due to the violence that took place last year. What he said had a lot of similarities with what we had heard from the shop owners at Nuh. He stated that the yatra in 2023 had clear intentions of creating disharmony among the people of the Mewat region and this year, this would not take place due to the presence of the police. He also brought forth the point of negligence from the side of the administration last year, stating how the Superintendent of Police was on leave and that there was no effort from the side of the state to regulate the procession, leading it to go out of hand. This year with the police being present and the absence of a lot of members from Bajrang Dal and VHP, there was no chance that a communal clash would take place.

We spoke to a farmer who was standing alongside the school teacher and he said that there have been minor incidents and disagreements between the Hindu and Muslim communities in the Mewat region, however, these were always resolved and they never escalated to a large-scale issue. The school teacher added that the Meo-Muslims of Mewat had a choice to go to Pakistan during the time of partition but they chose to stay in India because this was the land they considered home. He emphasised that the Meo-Muslims had a choice to leave and go, unlike the Hindus who had no choice, and the Meo-Muslims deciding to stay in India shows their patriotism and their commitment to the nation.

While this conversation was taking place, a rally of bikes with members who were participating in the yatra passed by shouting “Jai Shri Ram” loudly, directing it to where we were sitting. The farmer said this shows the nature of the procession—if one is undertaking a spiritual pilgrimage, why would they direct their slogans towards someone else; they should keep the sloganeering to themselves. Directing the slogan to someone else from a different community displays a provocative and aggressive characteristic.

7.5 Spiritual Nature of Yatris in Jhir Temple of Firozpur Jhirka

The Jhir Temple is located on the outskirts of Firozpur Jhirka on top of a hill. Here again, the presence of the police was very clear. There was a police chowki at the base of the hill and more police officers near the temple entrance, ensuring the traffic was passing by smoothly. Inside the temple, the yatris were making their way to the interior area, where the shivling was present. Here again, the behaviour of the yatris demonstrated how this year's yatra was a spiritual exercise in contrast to the politicised procession that took place last year. The organisers were present at the entrance of the temple, ensuring that the yatris would complete the ritual and head towards their respective vehicles and head for the temple in Singhar, so that no overcrowding would take place.

7.6 Conversation with Police and Residents of Firozpur Jhirka

We sat and conversed with the police who were present at the base of the hill. The police were very welcoming and offered us tea and water. When we asked them why they think violence took place during last year's yatra, one of the police officers simply replied that the communal clash only took place as they were not present. While he meant it as a boast about the efficiency of the police in ensuring peace and order, it is clear to see from his statement that in 2023, the gravest error from the side of the administration was the lack of the presence of the police. Another police officer stated that the directive they had been given from their superiors was that this yatra must take place without a single incident.

At Firozpur Jhirka, all the shops had been closed and every 100–200 metres, a few residents of the area were sitting and observing the yatra. We spoke to a few residents to understand their perception of the yatra. As the yatra had not reached the Jhir Temple, the Muslim residents of Firozpur Jhirka had no experience regarding the communal clash that took place in 2023, however, they were aware about what had taken place in Nuh and were vigilant to ensure that no incident would take place in their area. We asked them why all the shops were closed, to which they replied that this was a conscious decision taken by the people of the area. By closing the shops, they were ensuring people would not be gathering at any place and the roads would be empty as the procession vehicles passed. They went on to say that the elderly of the village had been positioned along the route of the procession inside of Firozpur Jhirka, and just like in Nuh they would ensure that no incident would take place, in terms of the youth getting provoked by the sloganeering of the procession.

One interesting point that was repeating itself from all the conversations that we had was on the characteristic of the procession. The resident of Firozpur Jhirka also repeated that if the procession is spiritual in nature, then the chance of violence immediately decreases. There is the likelihood of violence only if the procession members have an agenda of provoking and inciting communal tensions through loudspeakers, weapons, and communal slogans.

7.7 Post Procession Discussions with Residents of Nuh

After the procession, the CDPP team conducted a series of field interviews with residents of Nuh who witnessed both the processions of 2023 and 2024. The total sample size was 20 respondents, out of which 15 of the respondents were from the Muslim community and 5 were from the Hindu community. Through the discussions with the respondents, we see many themes arise in terms of how the residents of Nuh view the difference in how the state has responded to the processions, actions of the police, and their perception of the procession in general.

7.8 Nationalism as a Defense

In our conversation with the Muslim residents of Nuh after the commencement of the procession, what was very apparent was the guarded manner in which questions were answered. In the case of many respondents, when they were probed about who they felt was responsible for the violence that took place during the procession, the blame would be placed on the organisers of the processions who belonged to armed militant organisations such as the Bajrang Dal and VHP. However, with this answer, statements would accompany which described the role of the Meo- Muslims during the independence struggle. The Muslim respondents would describe how the Meo- Muslims refused to transition to Pakistan during the time of partition even though they had the choice to do so. The fact that they did not do so is a display of true nationalism. One of the respondents spoke about how the RSS and its members never had a test to display their dedication and commitment to the country, which the Meo-Muslims had done so during the time of partition.

What was very evident from the conversations with the respondents was that nationalism was used as a defense to ward away allegations that Meo-Muslims were against the state and the religious practices of different communities. Nationalism was evoked as a defense and counter to the allegations of communalism that was being placed on the Meo-Muslims. The respondents argued that there was no case of them harbouring ill will against those who would carry out the procession, provided that it was not violent and targeting those who belonged to the Muslim community. Recounting what had taken place during the 2023 procession, one of the respondents spoke about how the loudspeakers were playing obnoxious music which was targeted against the Muslim community and he asked how it is that the Meo-Muslims were being labelled as anti-national and communal. It is very clear to see that in the case of communal violence, the commitment of the Muslim community is always brought into question as part of right-wing anti-minority discourse. Thus, to counter this, the proof of burden of displaying one's nationalism falls on the Muslim community.

7.9 Brotherhood across Faiths within the Context of Nuh

When both the Muslim and Hindu respondents were asked about the nature of relationship that existed between the communities, both sides denied any case of ill will between the locals who were residing in Nuh. One of the respondents said that the beedi from which a Meo-Muslim smokes is the same from which a Hindu shares, brushing off any case of enmity that would be assumed would be present due to the scale of violence that took place. On the topic of brotherhood, one of the Hindu respondents stated that the Kanwar Yatra passed through Nuh every year and each year the Muslim residents would set up tents to welcome and provide hospitality to the yatri. He also added that the village had a culture of sharing festivals among its residents—during Eid Muslims would invite their Hindu neighbours, and the Hindus would do the same during the time of their festivities.

When one of the Muslim respondents was asked about whether there have been cases of

segregation between the Muslim and Hindu community after the violence of 2023, he responded saying that the neighbour he had for 30 years (who was a Hindu) was still his neighbour, asking why would any conflict ever arise with his neighbour. While discussing the nature of violence that

When one of the Muslim respondents was asked about whether there have been cases of segregation between the Muslim and Hindu community after the violence of 2023, he responded saying that the neighbour he had for 30 years (who was a Hindu) was still his neighbour, asking why would any conflict ever arise with his neighbour. While discussing the nature of violence that took place in 2023, a Hindu respondent spoke about how due to the violence he was not able to return to his residence. At this time, his neighbour had offered him refuge and told him to stay till the time the violence subsided. What was very clear to see from the respondents was an emphasis on how the lives of the residents who stayed in Nuh was interconnected in terms of dependence from an economic and social perspective. Many of the residents of Nuh, though hailing from different religious backgrounds, were in business with each other in terms of working together and purchasing amenities or services from the other. Due to the economic and social interdependence, the prospect of enmity between the communities did not arise, even after the violence in 2023. This was also mainly due to the fact that both communities attributed the cause of violence to outsiders.

7.10 How Is the State Perceived? Who Is the State Safeguarding?

There was a marked difference in how the state was perceived in terms of the responses that came from the members of the Hindu and Muslim community. While both the communities did not attribute the causes of violence on the residents of Nuh, who they believed was responsible for the violence was very visibly different. The Hindu respondents believed that the administration and police had not sufficiently curtailed those who aimed to disrupt the procession in 2023 and had pelted stones at yatis. They believed that the state had failed to stop those outsider Muslims who had come to Nuh with the objective of disrupting the procession due to it being linked with individuals such as Monu Manesar. The Muslim respondents blamed the state for allowing the procession to take place in the manner in which it did, being inflammatory and displaying communal characteristics that were extremely provocative in nature. They also blamed the state for being biased towards the members of the procession, as the whole onus of the violence was placed on members of the Muslim community. This was apparent in terms of who was arrested by the police and whose properties were demolished.

In the case of 2024, we do not see the Hindu or Muslim respondents viewing the state as an antagonist figure. Both communities were in praise of the manner in which the state had handled the event without any case of conflict or violence. When the respondents were asked who they felt the state was trying to safeguard and if they felt the state was against either the procession or the Muslim residents of Nuh it had earlier defamed, both sides responded by saying that the state had simply done its duty this time in terms of handling the procession. This shows that neither of the

communities viewed the state as an antagonistic actor due to the simple fact that it had carried out its duty without any bias or prejudice. Hence, we can see that the perception of the state and the characteristics attributed to it depend heavily on the manner which the state operates and carries out its duties.

7.11 Religious Rituals in Public Spaces

When the Hindu respondents were asked about what they felt about the procession and whether it had any ritual significance to them, they agreed that the procession was fairly new in terms of its inception. During earlier times, a much smaller procession would be carried out only by the locals of Nuh towards the Shiv Mandir however, now it has become a large scale event attracting many members from outside. While they were not opposed to the nature of the procession in its present form, they did agree to the fact that it was not an established ritual and had been taken over by organisations and individuals from outside of Nuh. When asked about the inflammatory slogans and songs that were used in 2023, one of the Hindu respondents responded by saying that there is no place for that in religious practice and that there were malicious elements present. He contrasted the 2023 procession with the one that took place in the present year, saying that the change in the organizing committee made a huge difference in terms of the spirituality that was associated with the procession. He claimed that the 2023 procession felt more like a political rally in contrast to the procession of 2024, which paid heed to ritual significance and an actual celebration of God.

The Muslim respondents felt that the processions of 2023 and 2024 carried elements within that highlighted how it was not a pure religious ritual. In both years, with one being marked with violence, there were cases of sloganeering that was political in nature and had anti-Muslim sentiments. One of the Muslim respondents put emphasis on the fact that even if religious rituals or celebrations take place in public spaces, why should it have to attempt to antagonise members of a different community. During the discussion, he stated that it was clear from both the years, that due to this procession not being an established religious practice and due to it earlier being organised by the VHP and Bajrang Dal, it still had remnants of provocative attitudes from the outsider participants.

8. Takeaways

8.1 Role of Administration and Police in Maintaining Law and Order

We can see the difference between the approach of the government and the police in 2023 and 2024. Because the government and the police were not vigilant and present during 2023, militant Hindutva organisations such as VHP and Bajrang Dal were able to create a communal environment by using loudspeakers which were playing anti-Muslim music and shouting provocative slogans while brandishing weapons. In 2024, the entire procession was monitored

using drones, police were placed in zones which were thought to be sites where incidents of violence could take place, and the decision to ban loudspeakers and the carrying of weapons during the procession ensured that law and order prevailed.

8.2 Depoliticised Procession due to the Absence of Militant Hindutva Organisations in the Organising Committee

One major difference from last year's procession was the absence of VHP and Bajrang Dal in the organising committee of the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra. As the residents of Nuh we engaged with also stated, the nature of the procession was entirely different and this year it seemed more spiritual in nature. In contrast to last year's procession, which had elements that would foster a communal climate, this year's procession was focused more on the yatra rather than antagonising the Muslims of the region, which had been the primary focus when the yatra was organised by the VHP and Bajrang Dal. The absence of controversial communal figures such as Monu Manesar and Bittu Bajrangi from the yatra meant that there was no communal context in which the procession would take place. The emphasis by the organising committee of the yatra on maintaining peace and warning those who were partaking in provoking the Muslim residents of Nuh shows how the intent of the yatra was very different from last year's.

8.3 Role of the Muslims in Ensuring Peace and Brotherhood Prevailed

Alarmed with how the blame was placed on them, the Muslim residents of Nuh were determined to prove that the communal tag that was placed on them was false. The whole act of showering flowers on the members of the procession and providing them with refreshments was done with the intention to show that they were not against the processions and they wanted to make the yatri feel welcome. Additionally, the idea of closing all the shops and emptying the streets, while placing the elderly members on the main road to monitor and ensure that no one gets provoked by the procession was done to leave no possibility for violence.

9. Conclusion

It is clear to see with the example of the Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra that the attitude of the state, involvement of militant Hindutva groups in the organisation of the procession, and presence of weapons and loudspeakers play a huge role in turning a religious procession into a communal clash. The most important role is the one played by the administration and the police, who decide through their vigilance whether violence will occur or not. In 2022, multiple processions took place in Telangana, and none resulted in violence unlike in the other states. The major reason for this being that the state had the political will to ensure that law and order would be maintained. The 2024 Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra is a very good example of that. Apart from political will, another important development that took place in between both iterations of the Brajmandal

Jalabhishek Yatra of 2023 and 2024 was the changing sociopolitical condition due to the election results of 2024, where the Bharatiya Janata Party lost its outright majority in parliament. As the Routes of Wrath report (2023) shows, states where the Bharatiya Janata Party was in power saw higher rates of violence through religious processions and inaction from the side of the administration and the police. For further study, it would be important and interesting to study the connection between who is in power at the Centre and the way communal clashes take place through religious processions.

From the conversations that took place with the residents of Nuh following the procession, it is clear to see that the social and economic ties between the residents of Nuh had not been severed due to the processional violence. What is apparent is the role of outsiders who attempt to create discord and animosity in the name of religion. As Paul Brass had theorised about Institutionalised Riot Systems (2004), we can see politicised processions being carried out in the name of religion which possess an agenda of impacting the social and economic ties between the residents of a certain area. While in the case of Nuh, this did not succeed, there are many other contexts where post violence the social relations between members of different communities have worsened.

It has become very apparent that violence during processions is rarely random or spontaneous. It is fostered and encouraged by many factors, the most prominent being the role of the state and the agenda with which the procession is being carried out. We will end the report with a quote from Dr. Peter van de Veer (1996) in his academic paper “Riots and Rituals: The Construction of Violence and Public Space in Hindu Nationalism” where he writes, “Those who perpetrate the violence are often characterized as 'fanatic' members of mobs led astray by irresponsible leaders. It is this discourse which obfuscates the important connections between riots and rituals in the modern world.” Thus, the state needs to be present to ensure that law and order takes precedence over all else and allocate the blame on the militant Hindutva groups responsible for provoking violence, not on the minority Muslim community who are the victims of the violence.

References

Akhtar, S. (2023, August 4). Haryana violence: An age-old yatra exemplifying harmony. Hindustan Times. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/gurugram-news/peaceful-coexistence-hindu-and-muslim-communities-unite-during-mewat-s-84-kos-yatra-in-haryana-101691088038558.html>

Association for Protection of Civil Rights. (2023). Beyond the surface: Exposing systemic violence and police complicity: A fact-finding report on Nuh violence. APCR India.

Braj Mandal Yatra begins in Haryana's Nuh amid tight security. (2024, July 22). The Hindu. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/braj-mandal-yatra-begins-in-haryanas-nuh-amid-tight-security/article68431643.ece>

Braj Mandal Yatra takes place peacefully in Gurugram and Nuh, Muslims shower flowers. (2024, July 22). Hindusthan Samachar English. <https://english.hindusthansamachar.in/Encyc/2024/7/22/Braj-Mandal-Yatra-took-place-peacefully-in-Gurugra.php>

Brass, P. R. (2004). The production of Hindu-Muslim violence in contemporary India. University of Washington Press.

Chakraborty, D. (2023, March 30). "Who are Delhi police to stop us": Ram Navami rally brings back memories of violence in Jahangirpuri. ThePrint. <https://theprint.in/india/who-are-delhi-police-to-stop-us-ram-navami-rally-brings-back-memories-of-violence-in-jahangirpuri/1484495/>

Citizens & Lawyers Initiative. (2023). Routes of wrath: Weaponizing religious processions; Communal violence during Ram Navami and Hanuman Jayanti April 2022. Chander Uday Singh for Citizens & Lawyers Initiative.

CJP Team. (2022, December 12). What was CJP's PIL seeking directions for implementation of law for regulation of religious processions all about? CJP. <https://cjp.org.in/what-was-cjps-pil-seeking-directions-for-implementation-of-law-for-regulation-of-religious-processions-all-about/>

Clashes break out between two groups during VHP procession in Haryana's Nuh; Prohibitory orders imposed. (2023, August 1). The Hindu. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece>

Farooqui, R. M. (2023, August 3). Deadly communal violence flares in India a month before world leader summit. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2023/08/02/india/india-train-shooting-communal-violence-gurugram-intl-hnk/index.html>

Gaborieau, M. (1985). From Al-Beruni to Jinnah: Idiom, ritual and ideology of the Hindu--Muslim confrontation in South Asia. *Anthropology Today*, 1(3), pp. 7–14.

Gupta, N. (2018). Performing processions: Claiming the city. In *Religion and the city in India*. Routledge.

Jaffrelot, C. (1998). The politics of processions and Hindu–Muslim riots. In *Community conflict and the state in India* Oxford University Press.

Jaffrelot, C. (2009). The Hindu nationalist reinterpretation of pilgrimage in India: The limits of Yatra politics. *Nations and Nationalism* Cornell University Press.

Jain, R. (2023, August 3). Hindu- Muslim riots expose risk at major Indian business hub. *Reuters.com*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece>

Kaur, R. (2003). *Performative politics and the cultures of Hinduism: Public uses of religion in western India* Anthem Press.

Centre for Study of Society and Secularism (2023, January 24). *Khargone violence—Fact finding report*. <https://csss-islam.com/fact-finding-reports/khargone-violence-fact-finding-report/>

Kissu, S. (2024, July 21). Internet snapped, no VHP or Bajrang DAL in organising committee. Nuh ready for Jalabhishek Yatra. *ThePrint*. <https://theprint.in/india/internet-snapped-no-vhp-or-bajrang-dal-in-organising-committee-nuh-ready-for-jalabhishek-yatra/2184293/>

Maniyar, Z. (2023, July 14). What was CJP's PIL seeking directions for implementation of law for regulation of religious processions all about? *CJP*. <https://cjp.org.in/what-was-cjps-pil-seeking-directions-for-implementation-of-law-for-regulation-of-religious-processions-all-about/>

Nuh police chief, on leave when communal violence began, transferred to Bhiwani. (2023, August 4). *The Wire*. https://thewire.in/security/nuh-police-chief-on-leave-when-communal-violence-began-transferred-to-bhiwani/?mid_related_new

Officials to use drones to monitor Brij Mandal Jalabhishek Yatra at Sohna. (2024, July 21). *The Tribune*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece>

Pandit, D. (2022, December 20). Hindutva pop: The soundtrack to India's anti-Muslim movement. *TIME*. <https://time.com/6242156/hindutva-pop-music-anti-muslim-violence-india/>

Rajagopal, K. (2023, April 4). Months before ram Navami violence, SC dismissed a petition highlighting how religious processions are being “weaponised.” *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece>

Ramu, M. (2022, April 30). Formulate guidelines on permission to religious programmes: HC. *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece>

“Religious freedom worsened”: US body names India as “Country of particular concern.” (2022, April 22). *The Wire*. <https://thewire.in/communalism/religious-freedom-worsened-us-body-names-india-as-country-of-particular-concern>

Report by citizen-lawyer collective highlights how routes chosen for religious processions trigger communal riots. (2023, March 26). *The Hindu*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece-routes-chosen-for-religious-processions-trigger-communal-riots/article66661280.ece>

Shah, G. (1970). Communal riots in Gujarat—Report of a preliminary investigation. *Economic and Political Weekly*.

Started as pilgrimage, Brajmandal Jalabhishek Yatra turned into power show in last three years. (2023, August 3). *The Tribune*. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/haryana-nuh-gurugram-clashes-violence-july-31-2023/article67142736.ece-pilgrimage-brajmandal-jalabhishek-yatra-turned-into-power-show-in-last-three-years-531437/>

Tejani, S. (2007). *Indian secularism: A social and intellectual history, 1890–1950*. Indiana University Press.

Vadodara ram Navami violence: Unabated expression of hegemony and impunity enjoyed by Hindu right. (2023, October 26). *Centre for Study of Society and Secularism*. <https://csss-islam.com/fact-finding-reports/vadodara-ram-navami-violence-unabated-expression-of-hegemony-and-impunity-enjoyed-by-hindu-right/>

Veer, P. V. (1996). Riots and rituals: The construction of violence and public space in Hindu nationalism. In *Riots and Pogroms*. New York University Press.

CDPP Honorary Governing Council

G Sudhir, IAS (Retd) is the Founder and Director of CDPP. He served as Special Chief Secretary in undivided Andhra Pradesh and was also Chairman of the 2015 Commission of Inquiry to study socio-economic and educational conditions of Muslims in Telangana.

Syed Adeeluddin is the Director of CDPP. He is a philanthropist and social worker juggling his family construction business alongside. He is an engineering graduate of Osmania University, and has completed his MBA (Finance).

Amir Ullah Khan is a member of the Telangana State Public Service Commission. He is a development economist and former civil servant, and also Adjunct Professor at MCRHRDI of Government of Telangana.

Neelima Khetan is the Managing Partner at Nous Consulting. A social sector advisor with experience in non-profits, CSR, sustainable and rural development, she has previously headed the CSR divisions for Coca-Cola, Vedanta Group and Hindustan Zinc.

Amitabh Kundu is currently Distinguished Fellow at Research and Information System for Developing Countries. He was Dean of School of Social Sciences, JNU. He also served as Chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee.

Saleema Razvi is a research economist at Copenhagen Consensus Center. She has previously worked in organisations like Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations, Population Foundation of India and UNICEF.

Abdul Shaban is a professor at Centre for Public Policy, Habitat and Human Development, School of Development Studies, TISS, Mumbai. He has also been visiting Professor/fellow at several leading universities such as the LSE, Muenster University, Erasmus University and Paris Diderot University.

Jeemol Unni is a professor at Ahmedabad University. She is former Director and RBI Chair Professor of Economics at Institute of Rural Management, Anand. A specialist in labour economics, she is Editorial Board member of Indian Journal of Labour Economics and Journal of Development Policy and Practice.

Aalok Wadhwa is a management professional with around three decades of experience working in FMCG, online and social media content, publishing and retail businesses. A graduate of St. Stephen's College, he has an MBA from IIM-B.

Sumaira Naser is a philanthropist, educationist and an environmentalist. She is also a patron for the 'Telangana Science Fair Academy' which promotes scientific temperament amongst youth, an advisor at the 'International Women's Startup Corridor' (IWSC) with a focus to promote women's health.

Rathin Roy is Distinguished Professor at the Kautilya School of Public Policy, GITAM University, Hyderabad, and a former member of the Economic Advisory Council to the Prime Minister.

Research Team

Amitabh Kundu is a Senior Fellow at WRI India and has been the chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by the Ministry of Minority Affairs.

Soma Wadhwa is a development studies researcher with extensive experience as a media professional.

Nahia Hussain is the Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP with a Master's from the National Law School of India, Bangalore.

Anjana Divakar is the Executive Director of Public Policy Research and Operations at the Centre for Development Policy and Practice (CDPP).

Apoorva Ramachandra is a research associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Economics from the Jindal School of Government and Public Policy.

Moumita Barman is a research associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Public Policy and Governance from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad

Laldinmoi Pangamte is the Copy Editor of publications at CDPP. She has a PhD degree from the School of International Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi.

Ablaz Mohammed Schemnad is a research associate at CDPP. He has done his master's in Development Studies from Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad with a semester from Sciences Po Lille, France.

Rashad Ullah Khan is a senior research fellow at CDPP. Previously, he worked as an Academic Associate at the Kautilya School of Public Policy. He completed his Master's in Women's Studies from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.

Mohammed Zaid Khan is a junior fellow in Media and Communications at CDPP. He is pursuing his Bachelor's degree in Commerce Analytics from St. Mary's College, Hyderabad.

Mohammed Yaqoob Quraishi is the Manager of operations & Finance at CDPP. He has a degree in Commerce from Osmania University.

Our Publications

- Gender and Inclusion Series
- Citizenship Series
- Aata Hai Yaad Mujhko Guzra Hua Zamana
- Muslims in Uttar Pradesh
- India's Infrastructure Challenges
- Journal of Development Policy and Practice
- Alfaz Ki Mehfil – Edition I, II and III
- Introduction to International Finance
- Wajood-e-Muslim
- Agriculture in Telangana
- Daman-e-Gulchein

Series – 2022

- Situating Development of Muslims in Uttar Pradesh
- Education Challenges: Quality and Inclusion
- How Healthy is our Young Population?
- Muslim Women Tackling Vulnerability and Marginalisation

Series – 2023

- Internet Control and the Rise of Discrimination in India
- Agriculture in Telangana : from Plight to Pride
- The World's Biggest Country : India's Demographic Trajectory and its impact on Muslims, the Parliament, and the Labour Market
- From Speech to Action : Exploring Hate Speech Origins, Impact, and Interventions from Multidisciplinary Perspectives

Series – 2024

- Diversity and Disparities: A Study on Caste, Religion, Gender, and Disability in Higher Education in India
- Workforce Participation in India : Where are the women?

The CDPP brings out a quarterly working paper based on the research work being carried out here. These are published on our website www.cdpp.co.in and sent to a select group for review, comments, and critique.

CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE

Serene Heights Buildings, #10-3-303, Masab Tank,
Hyderabad-500028, T.S., India.

info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in | +91 9391581698